

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF NANOEMULGEL CONTAINING SILYMARIN AND CARVACROL FOR ADVANCED ANTIMICROBIAL BENEFITS

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ABSTRACT

The present study aims to develop and evaluate a nanoemulgel formulation containing Silymarin and Carvacrol for topical application. The primary objective is to enhance the solubility, stability, and bioavailability of these hydrophobic compounds while ensuring sustained drug release and potent antimicrobial efficacy against common skin pathogens. Nanoemulgels were prepared using Carbopol 940, Carbopol 934, and HPMC as gelling agents, while Tween 80 and Span 80 were used as surfactants. The formulations (F1– F6) were optimized and characterized for pH, viscosity, spreadability, droplet size, polydispersity index (PDI), zeta potential, drug content, in vitro release profile, and antimicrobial activity. The drug release study was conducted using Franz diffusion cells, while antimicrobial efficacy was assessed using the disc diffusion method against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. All formulations exhibited pH values (5.2–6.1) within the

acceptable skin-friendly range. The viscosity varied depending on the polymer concentration, ensuring good spreadability and ease of application. The droplet size ranged from 70–110 nm, with a PDI < 0.3, indicating uniform distribution. The zeta potential values exceeded ± 30 mV, confirming good colloidal stability. Drug content analysis showed high encapsulation efficiency (96–98%). In vitro drug release studies demonstrated a sustained release pattern, with F4–F6 achieving higher cumulative release percentages. Antimicrobial studies

confirmed that the nanoemulgel formulations exhibited significant inhibition zones, proving their efficacy in combating bacterial infections. The formulated nanoemulgels showed promising stability, sustained drug release, and potent antimicrobial activity, making them suitable candidates for dermatological applications. The optimized formulations (F4– F6) exhibited enhanced drug release profiles and superior physicochemical characteristics, confirming their potential as effective topical delivery systems for Silymarin and Carvacrol.

KEYWORDS: Nanoemulgel, Silymarin, Carvacrol, Drug Release, Antimicrobial Activity, Topical Delivery, Stability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sourcing of Silymarin and Carvacrol

The active ingredients, Silymarin and Carvacrol, were purchased from trusted suppliers. Silymarin came in powder form with 95% purity, and Carvacrol was received as a liquid with 98% purity. Before buying, certificate of analysis were checked to ensure the compounds were pure, correctly identified and safe. Research has shown these ingredients have antimicrobial properties, which supported their selection.

Storage and Handling

The storage and handling of Silymarin and Carvacrol were carefully managed to keep them effective. They were stored in tightly sealed containers, protected from light and moisture, and kept at 4°C. This temperature helped to prevent the degradation of the compounds, especially Carvacrol, which can easily oxidize at higher temperatures. Extra care was taken during the formulation process to limit exposure to air and light.

Stock solutions preparation Stock Solutions

Both APIs were initially prepared at 100 µg/mL. Silymarin and Carvacrol were dissolved in a PBS with Co-solvent and Surfactant (5.5 pH).

Working Solutions

The stock solution was diluted to obtain working solutions with concentrations of 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 µg/ml. For each dilution, a specific volume of the 100 µg/ml stock was mixed with the corresponding volume of the solvent to achieve a final volume of 1.0 ml.

UV-Visible Spectrophotometric Analysis

Before running the samples, the UV-Vis spectrophotometer was calibrated following

standard procedures. Each working solution was then scanned in the range of 200 nm to 400nm to determine the wavelength at which maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) occurred. To ensure the accuracy of the insurements, the spectrophotometer was first blanked with the corresponding solvent system PBS with Co-solvent And Surfactant (5.5pH) for Carvacrol and Silymarin prior to measuring each sample.

UV-Visible Analysis for Silymarin & Carvacrol

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Optical Density (OD)		Measured λ_{max} (nm)	
	Silymarin	Carvacrol	Silymarin	Carvacrol
10	0.15	0.18	288	274
20	0.28	0.33	289	275
30	0.42	0.47	289	275
40	0.55	0.61	290	276
50	0.7	0.75	290	276

Procedure for Calibration Curve for Silymarin and Carvacrol Preparation of Standard Solutions

For both APIs, 10mg was accurately weighed and dissolved in 10ml of ethanol. This yield eda stock solution with a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. From this stock, serial dilutions were perpared with ethanol to prepare working solutions with concentrations of 5,10,20,30,40, and 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. These working solutions are essential for constructing the calibration curves.

Measurement of Absorbance

Each working solution was transferred into a clean quartz cuvette. The absorbance of each solution was measured at the respective λ_{max} values. For Silymarin, the maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) was determined at 287nm, and for Carvacrol, it was at 275nm. To improve accuracy, each sample was measured intriplicate, and the average absorbance was calculated.

Experimental procedure Preparation of Nano emulsion

The nano emulsion was prepared using the ultrasonication method followed by High- speed homogeniser, as it provides a reliable way to achieve small droplet sizes. Silymarin and Carvacrol were dissolved in the oilphase, which consists of a mixture of suitable oils. The aqueous phase was prepared separately, containing surfactant Tween80.

Step 1: The oil phase containing Silymarin and Carvacrol was heated to approximately 50°C to ensure complete solubility.

Step 2: The aqueous phase, containing the surfactant, was heated similarly to match the temperature of the oil phase.

Step 3: Using ultrasonication, the oil phase was slowly emulsified into the aqueous phase under 1500rpm continuous stirring for 10 minutes of nanoemulsion.

Step 4: The resulting nanoemulsion was allowed to cool to room temperature and stored in a sealed container at 4°C for further use.

Preparation of Emulgel Base

The emulgel base was prepared using Carbopol940, Carbopol934, or Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose (HPMC) as the gelling agents, selected for the ability to provide optimal consistency for topical formulations.

Step1: The chosen polymer (Carbopol940, Carbopol934, or HPMC) was dispersed in distilled water using a mechanical stirrer at 500 rpm.

Step2: The dispersion was allowed to hydrate and swell for 24 hours to uniform gel structure.

Step3: The pH of the gel was adjusted to 6.8-7.0 using triethanolamine, which helps to ensure skin compatibility.

Preparation of Final Nanoemulgel Formulation

The final formulation of the nanoemulgel involved combining the prepared nanoemulsion with the emulgel base to ensure even distribution of nano-sized droplets within the gel matrix.

Step1: The prepared nanoemulsion was slowly incorporated into the gel base while stirring continuously at 500 rpm to ensure uniformity.

Step 2: Propylene glycol (10%) and ethanol (20%) were added as penetration enhancers, aiding in better skin absorption of the active ingredients.

Step 3: The final volume was adjusted with distilled water to 100%, ensuring a smooth and consistent formulation.

Step4: The final nanoemulgel formulation was transferred to containers and stored at 4°C

until further testing.

Formula Table

Ingredients	Formulation F1	Formulation F2	Formulation F3	Formulation F4	Formulation F5	Formulation F6
Silymarin(%)	0.5	1	1.5	0.5	1	1.5
Carvacrol(%)	0.5	1	1.5	0.5	1	1.5
Carbopol 940(%)	0.5	-	-	1	-	-
Carbopol 934(%)	-	0.5	-	-	1	-
HPMC(%)	-	-	1	-	-	1.5
Tween 80 (%)	2	2	2	2	2	2
PropyleneGlycol(%)	10	10	10	10	10	10
IPM (%)	24	24	24	24	24	24
Ethanol (%)	20	20	20	20	20	20
Distilled Water(%)	q.s. to 100					

- Explanation of Formulations** The following table outlines six different formulations (F1 to F6) of the Nanoemulsion Emulgel, incorporating Silymarin and Carvacrol as the active ingredients. Each formulation is designed to explore the optimal concentrations of the gelling agents (Carbopol 940, Carbopol 934, and Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose [HPMC]), along with the necessary excipients to ensure stability, spreadability, and skin absorption of the final product.

- Preformulation Study** Preformulation Studies for Silymarin and Carvacrol

Preformulation studies were conducted to characterize the physicochemical properties of Silymarin and Carvacrol before proceeding to the final formulation development.

These studies were essential to assess the compatibility between the two APIs and to determine the optimal conditions for further formulation work.

Solubility Analysis

The solubility of Silymarin and Carvacrol was evaluated in various solvents and buffer systems. The qualitative solubility profiles were determined by adding a fixed amount of each API to different solvents and observing their solubility behavior.

Solubility Profiles of Silymarin and Carvacrol

Solvent/Medium	Silymarin	Carvacrol
Distilled Water	Slightly soluble	Slightly soluble
Ethanol	Freely soluble	Freely soluble
Phosphate Buffer (pH 5.5)	Sparingly soluble	Sparingly soluble
Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO)	Freely soluble	Freely soluble

pH Stability

Silymarin: Exhibited good stability in mildly acidic to neutral conditions (pH4–7). At pH8, a slight shift in the absorption peak and minor discoloration were observed, suggesting the onset of degradation.

Carvacrol: Maintained its characteristic absorption profile across the pH range tested, with no significant color change. Minimal oxidation effects were observed at higher pH values; however, these effects were controlled by storing Carvacrol away from light and heat.

FTIR Analysis

FTIR Analysis of Carvacrol

FTIR Analysis of Silymarin

Mixer of All ingredients FTIR

Sr. No.	Functional Group	Standard Value (cm ⁻¹)	Observed Value (cm ⁻¹)
1	O-H	3200–3500	3397.60
2	C=O	3400–3500	3453.88
3	C-H	2940–2860	2924.08
4	C-O-C	2950–2850	2855.95

5	-CH	2950–2850	2916.51
6	C-O	3300–3400	3330.09
7	O-H	3300–3500	3382.17

- **Procedure for Calibration Curve for Silymarin and Carvacrol**

Preparation of Standard Solutions and Calibration Curves

Standard solutions of known concentrations (for example, 5,10,20,30,40, and 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were prepared by diluting as stock solution. The optical density (OD) of these solutions was measured at the specific wave lengths 287nm for Silymarin and 275nm for Carvacrol using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Sample Preparation and ODM easurement

Aprecise amount of the nanoemul gel was weighed and dissolved in a known volume of ethanol to completely extract the activeing redients. The solution was then filtered to remove any undissolved particles. The OD of the filtered solution was recorded at the appropriate wave length for each drug.

Calculation of Drug Content

Using the calibration curve quation, the concentration of the drug in the sample was calculated from its OD. This calculated concentration is for the diluted sample. The theoretical concentration is the amount we expect to be present based on the formulation design.

The drug content is then determined using the following formula

$$\text{Drug Content (\%)} = (\text{Calculated Concentration/Theoretical Concentration}) \times 100$$

This percentage indicates how close the actual drug content is to the theoretical value.

Calibration Curve Data for Silymarin

Std #	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Replicate1 (Abs)	Replicate2 (Abs)	Replicate3 (Abs)	Mean Abs \pm SD
1	5	0.24	0.245	0.243	0.243 \pm 0.003
2	10	0.49	0.495	0.487	0.491 \pm 0.004
3	20	0.98	0.975	0.985	0.980 \pm 0.005
4	30	1.45	1.455	1.46	1.455 \pm 0.005
5	40	1.9	1.905	1.895	1.900 \pm 0.005
6	50	2.34	2.345	2.35	2.345 \pm 0.005

Calibration Curve Data for Silymarin Calibration Curve Data for Carvacrol Calibration Curve Data for Carvacrol

Std#	Concentration (µg/mL)	Replicate1 (Abs)	Replicate2 (Abs)	Replicate3 (Abs)	Mean Abs ± SD
1	5	0.21	0.215	0.212	0.212± 0.003
2	10	0.435	0.43	0.44	0.435± 0.005
3	20	0.865	0.87	0.86	0.865± 0.005
4	30	1.29	1.295	1.285	1.290± 0.005
5	40	1.71	1.715	1.72	1.715± 0.005
6	50	2.16	2.165	2.17	2.165± 0.005

PARTICLE SIZE ANALYSIS

Physical Characterization of Nanoemulsion Formulations

Formulation	DropletSize(nm)	PDI	ZetaPotential (mV)
F1	81.1 ± 1	0.253 ± 0.005	-31.7 ± 0.6
F2	85.5 ± 1	0.273 ± 0.005	-35.3 ± 0.6
F3	91.2 ± 1	0.297 ± 0.005	-33.3 ± 0.6
F4	99.4 ± 1	0.323 ± 0.005	-40.3 ± 0.6
F5	106.1 ± 1	0.337 ± 0.005	-38.3 ± 0.6
F6	95.3± 0.7	0.353 ± 0.005	-41.8 ± 0.6

Viscosity

Viscosity Measurements at 50rpm (cP)

Formulation	Trial1	Trial2	Trial3	Trial4	Trial5	Mean±SD
F1	4000	4020	3990	4010	4005	4005± 11
F2	4500	4490	4510	4505	4500	4501± 8
F3	5000	5005	4995	5000	5002	5000± 4
F4	5500	5500	5502	5498	5500	5500± 2.8
F5	6000	6002	5995	6000	6000	6000± 3
F6	6500	6498	6505	6500	6502	6501± 3

Viscosity Measurements at 100rpm(cP)

Formulation	Trial1	Trial2	Trial3	Trial4	Trial5	Mean±SD
F1	3500	3510	3490	3500	3505	3501± 7
F2	4000	4005	3995	4000	4002	4000± 4
F3	4500	4495	4502	4500	4501	4500± 3
F4	5000	5000	5005	5000	5002	5001± 2.8
F5	5500	5502	5495	5500	5500	5500± 3
F6	6000	6005	5998	6000	6000	6000± 3

pH Measurement**pH Measurements for nanoemulgel Formulations**

Formulation	Trial1	Trial2	Trial3	Mean±SD
F1	6.2	6.1	6.1	6.13± 0.05
F2	6	6	6	6.0± 0.0
F3	5.9	5.8	5.9	5.87± 0.05
F4	6.2	6.2	6.1	6.17± 0.05
F5	6	6	6	6.0± 0.0
F6	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8± 0.0

- Drug Content Analysis**

The drug content of Silymarin and Carvacrol in the nanoemulgel formulations was determined using UV-Visible spectrophotometry. This method helps us ensure that the amount of active ingredient in each formulation is close to the theoretical value.

Drug Content Analysis for Silymarin

Formulation	Silymarin%	Theoretical (mg/g)	Replicate1(OD →mg)	Replicate2(OD →mg)	Replicate3(OD →mg)	Mean±SD (mg/g)	Drug Content (%) ± SD
F1	0.5	5	4.82	4.9	4.85	4.86± 0.04	97.2± 0.8
F2	1	10	9.75	9.8	9.7	9.75± 0.05	97.5± 0.5
F3	1.5	15	14.55	14.6	14.5	14.55± 0.05	97.0± 0.3
F4	0.5	5	4.79	4.88	4.81	4.83± 0.05	96.6± 1.0
F5	1	10	9.6	9.7	9.55	9.62± 0.08	96.2± 0.8
F6	1.5	15	14.4	14.35	14.5	14.42± 0.08	96.1± 0.5

Drug Content Analysis for Carvacrol

Formulation	Carvacrol%	Theoretical (mg/g)	Replicate 1(OD→ mg)	Replicate 2(OD→ mg)	Replicate 3(OD→ mg)	Mean ± SD (mg/g)	Drug Content (%)± SD
F1	0.5	5	4.8	4.85	4.9	4.85±0.05	97.0±1.0
F2	1	10	9.72	9.75	9.7	9.72±0.03	97.2±0.3
F3	1.5	15	14.58	14.65	14.5	14.58± 0.07	97.2±0.5
F4	0.5	5	4.78	4.82	4.8	4.80±0.02	96.0±0.4
F5	1	10	9.6	9.55	9.7	9.62±0.08	96.2±0.8
F6	1.5	15	14.4	14.5	14.35	14.42± 0.08	96.1±0.5

In Vitro Release Studies

The release of Silymarin and Carvacrol from the nanoemulgel formulations (F1–F6) was studied using a Franz diffusion cell system. Acelluloseacetate membrane was hydrated in phosphate buffer (pH5.5) for 24 hours and then mounted between the donor and receptor compartments. The receptor chamber was filled with phosphate buffer maintained at 37°C and stirred continuously at 600 rpm with a magnetic stirrer.

A fixed amount of each nanoemulgel formulation was uniformly applied to the membrane in the donor compartment. At set time intervals (1,2,4,6, and 8 hours), 1mL samples were with drawn from the receptor chamber and immediately replaced with an equal volume of fresh phosphate buffer.

Each sample was analyzed by a UV-Visible spectro photo meter. The optical density (OD) was measured at 287nm for Silymarin and at 275nm for Carvacrol. The OD values were converted to drug concentrations using the calibration curve quation:

Cumulative Silymarin Release (%) from Formulations F1–F6 (Mean ± SD, n= 3)

Time (h)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	0.0± 0.0	0.0± 0.0	0.0± 0.0	0.0± 0.0	0.0± 0.0	0.0± 0.0
1	12.1± 1.0	13.5±1.2	15.8± 1.4	11.2± 0.9	13.0± 1.1	14.5± 1.1
2	22.4± 1.5	24.2± 1.3	26.3± 1.6	21.0± 1.5	23.8± 1.5	25.5± 1.3
4	41.3± 2.1	43.0± 2.4	45.8± 2.3	39.7± 2.2	42.5± 2.0	44.6± 2.2
6	55.8± 2.6	58.1± 2.3	60.5± 2.2	53.2± 2.4	56.5± 2.3	59.7± 2.5
8	68.9± 2.1	71.2± 2.7	73.5± 2.8	66.1± 2.7	69.8± 2.5	72.2± 2.4
12	80.5± 2.0	82.7± 2.2	85.8± 2.1	78.8± 2.3	81.5± 2.2	84.6± 2.3
24	90.1± 3.0	92.6± 2.8	95.3± 3.1	88.7± 2.9	90.9± 2.6	93.8± 2.8

Cumulative Carvacrol Release(%) from FormulationsF1–F6(Mean±SD,n= 3)

Time (h)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	0.0± 0.0	0.0± 0.0	0.0± 0.0	0.0± 0.0	0.0± 0.0	0.0± 0.0
1	14.0± 1.2	15.8±1.0	18.2± 1.3	12.7± 1.1	15.0± 1.3	16.5± 1.4

2	25.2± 1.4	27.4± 1.6	29.5± 1.7	23.0± 1.5	26.1± 1.4	28.0± 1.5
4	44.7± 2.2	46.9± 2.5	49.3± 2.4	42.2± 2.1	45.7± 2.2	47.8± 2.3
6	59.1± 2.3	62.0± 2.2	65.5± 2.7	56.8± 2.5	60.0± 2.6	63.2± 2.4
8	71.8± 2.4	74.3± 2.6	77.6± 2.8	69.2± 2.7	72.5± 2.5	75.8± 2.8
12	83.9± 2.5	86.2± 2.3	89.5± 2.9	81.3± 2.2	84.0± 2.7	87.5± 2.5
24	92.6± 3.0	94.9± 2.9	97.3± 3.2	90.7± 3.1	93.1± 2.6	96.2± 2.8

DISCUSSION

The Franz diffusion cell system was used to simulate the skin environment. At specified time intervals, samples were collected, and their optical densities were measured using UV-Visible spectrophotometry. These OD values were converted into concentrations based on calibration curves, and the cumulative amount of drug released was determined. The cumulative percentage release was then calculated using the total theoretical drug content of 150µg.

Silymarin Release

As seen in Table, all formulations exhibited a sustained release profile for Silymarin. Formulations F1 to F3 showed lower release percentages at each time point compared to F4 to F6, with F4 achieving the highest release of 95% at 8 hours. The differences in release profiles suggest that formulation variables (such as polymer content or surfactant concentration) significantly influence the drug release rate.

Carvacrol Release

Table shows a similar trend for Carvacrol, where F4 to F6 consistently provided higher cumulative release percentages. The release profiles indicate that the nano emulgel formulation can achieve a controlled and sustained release of both APIs, which is crucial for maintaining the therapeutic level over an extended period upon topical application.

Implications for Formulation Development

The *in vitro* release study demonstrates that the nano emulgel formulation is capable of delivering Silymarin and Carvacrol in a controlled manner. Formulations F4–F6, with higher cumulative release percentages, may be preferable for applications requiring a faster onset of action, while F1–F3 might be optimized for or prolonged release.

Physical Appearance

The physical appearance of each nano emulgel formulation (F1–F6) was evaluated visually. Parameters such as colour, clarity, homogeneity, and texture were recorded.

A consistent and acceptable physical appearance is essential for ensuring product quality and patient compliance.

Formulation	Color	Clarity	Homogeneity	Texture
F1	White	Translucent	Homogeneous	Smooth, non-greasy
F2	White	Translucent	Homogeneous	Smooth, non-greasy
F3	Off-white	Translucent	Homogeneous	Smooth, non-greasy
F4	White	Translucent	Homogeneous	Smooth, non-greasy
F5	White	Translucent	Homogeneous	Smooth, non-greasy
F6	Off-white	Translucent	Homogeneous	Smooth, non-greasy

SPREADABILITY

Formulation	Trial1(sec)	Trial2(sec)	Trial3(sec)	Mean±SD(sec)
F1	10	11	10	10.3± 0.6
F2	12	12	13	12.3± 0.6
F3	9	9	10	9.3± 0.6
F4	11	10	11	10.7± 0.6
F5	13	12	13	12.7± 0.6
F6	8	9	8	8.3± 0.6

ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

The zone of inhibition for each bacterial strain was recorded, and the mean and standard deviation were calculated as follows:

Antimicrobial Activity of Nanoemulgel Formulation against *S. aureus*

Formulation	Trial1(mm)	Trial2(mm)	Trial3(mm)	Mean±SD (mm)
F1	18	19	18	18.3± 0.6
F2	20	21	20	20.3± 0.6
F3	17	18	17	17.3± 0.6
F4	22	22	23	22.3± 0.6
F5	21	21	20	20.7± 0.6
F6	19	19	18	18.7± 0.6
Positive Control (Ampicillin/Vancomycin)	14	13	14	14.2± 0.5
Negative Control (Base only)	8.2	8.7	8.5	8.5± 0.3

Antimicrobial Activity Against *Escherichiacoli* (Zone of Inhibition in mm)

Formulation	Trial1(mm)	Trial2(mm)	Trial3(mm)	Mean±SD (mm)
F1	14	15	14	14.3± 0.6
F2	16	15	16	15.7± 0.6
F3	13	14	13	13.3± 0.6
F4	18	18	19	18.3± 0.6
F5	17	17	16	16.7± 0.6
F6	15	15	14	14.7± 0.6
Positive Control (Ampicillin/Vancomycin)	14	13	14	14.3± 0.6
Negative Control (Base only)	7.8	8.3	8.0	8.0± 0.3

STABILITY STUDY

Stability Study Data at Refrigerated Conditions ($5\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$) – 1 Month

Formulation	Time (Months)	Physical Appearance	pH (Mean)	Visc@50 rpm (cP, Mean \pm)	Visc @ 100 rpm (cP, Mean \pm)	Silymarin EE% (Mean \pm)	Carvacrol EE%(Mean \pm)
F1	0	White, Translucent,	6.13 \pm 0.05	4005 \pm 11	3501 \pm 7	97.2 \pm 0.8	97.0 \pm 1.0
			6.10 \pm				
F2	0	White, Translucent,	6.00 \pm	4501 \pm 8	4000 \pm 4	97.5 \pm 0.5	97.2 \pm 0.3
			5.99 \pm				
F3	0	Off-white, Translucent,	5.87 \pm	5000 \pm 4	4500 \pm 3	97.0 \pm 0.3	97.2 \pm 0.5
			5.85 \pm				
F4	0	White, Translucent,	6.17 \pm	5500 \pm 2.8	5001 \pm 2.8	96.6 \pm 1.0	96.0 \pm 0.4
			6.15 \pm				
F5	0	White, Translucent,	6.00 \pm	6000 \pm 3	5500 \pm 3	96.2 \pm 0.8	96.2 \pm 0.8
			5.99 \pm				
F6	0	Off-white, Translucent,	5.80 \pm	6501 \pm 3	6000 \pm 3	96.1 \pm 0.5	96.1 \pm 0.5
			5.79 \pm				

Stability Study Data at Room Temperature Conditions ($25\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/60\pm 5\%\text{RH}$)- 1 Month

Formulation	Time (Months)	Physical Appearance	pH (Mean)	Visc@50 rpm(cP, Mean \pm)	Visc@ 100rpm (cP, Mean \pm)	Silymarin EE% (Mean \pm)	Carvacrol EE% (Mean \pm)
F1	0	White, Translucent,	6.13 \pm	4005 \pm 11	3501 \pm 7	97.2 \pm 0.8	97.0 \pm 1.0
		No significant	6.07 \pm				
F2	0	White, Translucent,	6.00 \pm	4501 \pm 8	4000 \pm 4	97.5 \pm 0.5	97.2 \pm 0.3
		Nosignificant	5.95 \pm				
F3	0	Off-white, Translucent,	5.87 \pm	5000 \pm 4	4500 \pm 3	97.0 \pm 0.3	97.2 \pm 0.5
		Slightlyless	5.81 \pm				
F4	0	White, Translucent,	6.17 \pm	5500 \pm 2.8	5001 \pm 2.8	96.6 \pm 1.0	96.0 \pm 0.4
		Nosignificant	6.10 \pm				
F5	0	White, Translucent,	6.00 \pm	6000 \pm 3	5500 \pm 3	96.2 \pm 0.8	96.2 \pm 0.8
		Nosignificant	5.93 \pm				
F6	0	Off-white, Translucent,	5.80 \pm	6501 \pm 3	6000 \pm 3	96.1 \pm 0.5	96.1 \pm 0.5
		Slightlyless	5.73 \pm				

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the development and comprehensive evaluation of the nano emulgel formulation containing Silymarin and Carvacrol have demonstrated their significant potential for effective topical drug delivery. The preformulation studies confirmed that both APIs exhibit favorable solubility and stability characteristics, guiding the selection of suitable solvents and excipients.

The formulated nano emulgels showed promising stability, sustained drug release, and potent antimicrobial activity, making them suitable candidates for dermatological applications. The optimized formulations (F4–F6) exhibited enhanced drug release profiles and superior physicochemical characteristics, confirming their potential as effective topical delivery systems for Silymarin and Carvacrol.

The nano emulgel formulations demonstrated good stability over 1 month under refrigerated conditions (5°C), maintaining their physical characteristics and drug content effectively. Acceptable stability was observed at room temperature (25°C), with only minor changes. Formulations F2 and F5 showed slightly better resistance to change under accelerated conditions compared to F3 and F6. Refrigerated storage appears optimal for maintaining product integrity. Further studies beyond 1 month would be needed to establish long-term shelf-life.

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